

Pre-service Teachers' Confidence in solving Numeracy Tasks

Kathy O' Sullivan¹, Niamh O' Meara², Merrilyn Goos³ and Paul Conway²

¹University of Galway, ²University of Limerick, ³University of the Sunshine Coast

In Ireland, teachers are required to teach numeracy across all subject disciplines. Therefore, Initial Teacher Education [ITE] standards require all teachers to possess an adequate level of numeracy themselves and profess positive dispositions towards teaching numeracy across the curriculum. This paper reports on a study that investigated 204 pre-service post-primary teachers' confidence in completing numeracy tasks. Analysis of questionnaire data from participants in three universities showed that pre-service teachers in the STEM disciplines are more confident in their ability to complete the numeracy tasks correctly than pre-service teachers in other disciplines. This is an issue of concern. If pre-service teachers of all disciplines are to teach for numeracy learning within their lessons, regardless of their subject discipline, then pre-service teachers of all disciplines will need to have an adequate level of numeracy themselves, along with confidence to support numeracy development within their specific subject discipline.

Keywords: Numeracy in Initial Teacher Education; Confidence in numeracy tasks; Numeracy for disciplinary learning

Introduction

It is clear that governments internationally have agreed that all citizens should have gained the necessary literacy and numeracy competencies to live and work in today's world (ACARA, 1997; Department of Education and Skills [DES], 2011). While there has been significant discourse both internationally and nationally regarding the development of numeracy within the school education systems, very often teachers are not confident in teaching numeracy across the curriculum. The Irish government has stressed the importance of all teachers teaching for numeracy learning across all subject disciplines (DES 2011, 2015). This paper reports on a study that explored the confidence of Irish pre-service post-primary school teachers in completing numeracy tasks correctly.

Background and Context

In 2011, the Teaching Council of Ireland, the regulatory body for the teaching profession in Ireland, published a policy on the continuum of Teacher Education. This document refers to equipping newly qualified teachers with competencies such as numeracy in order to address national priorities, such as a numerate society (The Teaching Council of Ireland, 2011). More recently, the Teaching Council of Ireland has set out Core Elements that need to be included in all Initial Teacher Education [ITE] programmes (The Teaching Council of Ireland, 2020). It states that pre-service teachers who are enrolled in an ITE programme should have the chance to improve their own numeracy capabilities and furthermore, should be supported in demonstrating their numeracy competencies within their subject discipline. This is a change from the Teaching Council's position in 2011. The most recent policy put forward acknowledges that pre-service teachers need to be supported in their mission to teach for numeracy learning, including their own personal numeracy capabilities and ITE programmes are required to support them in doing so (Teaching Council of Ireland, 2020). However, this can be a challenging task. For example, in the case of teaching for numeracy learning across

the school curriculum, some teachers who are not teachers of mathematics or STEM disciplines may feel they do not have the expertise or adequate knowledge of numeracy to incorporate it into their lessons. Often teachers do not feel confident in their teaching capabilities to teach “mathematics”, as it is referred to in the Literacy and Numeracy strategy, which in turn leads to higher levels of stress. Furthermore Callingham, Beswick and Ferme (2015) argue that if a teacher is not confident in their own mathematical capabilities, and teaches a subject such as Art or History, they will feel less equipped to develop mathematical ideas and less disposed towards focussing on numeracy. Therefore a challenge is evident whereby teachers’ awareness of numeracy in their subject area needs to be addressed. Research conducted in Australia by Forgasz and Leder (2016) with teachers of primary and post-primary schools assessed their confidence in answering numeracy tasks. They found that 70% of teachers who studied mathematics at third level were confident in their answer being correct in comparison to only 40% of teachers who had not studied mathematics at third level feeling confident in the answer they provided. If teachers are expected to teach for numeracy learning across all school subject disciplines, then they must first have confidence in their own numeracy capabilities.

In some countries educators have been encouraging teaching numeracy across all subject disciplines and different contexts outside of the mathematics classroom, and they consider this approach essential in the development of students’ numeracy capabilities (Bolstad 2019; DES 2015; Goos et al. 2019). As such, if students are to develop numeracy competencies outside of the mathematics classroom, then the teachers supporting these initiatives also need to have the confidence to support students in developing the necessary numeracy capabilities. As discussed previously, the literacy and numeracy strategy 2011 – 2020 is an effort by the Irish government and the DES to ensure that the young people of Ireland will be well equipped to use their numeracy skills in the workplace, which in turn will benefit the economic growth of the country (DES, 2011). Research has shown that in order for teachers to improve the numeracy capabilities of their students, teachers must first equip themselves with the necessary skills to develop their own understanding of how mathematical concepts and numeracy affect their own lives and their subject discipline (Goos et al, 2013; Forgasz and Hall, 2019). To gain insight into pre-service teachers’ confidence in their own numeracy capabilities, responses to 7 numeracy tasks were analysed to address the following research question: How confident are pre-service post-primary teachers in their own numeracy competencies?

Research Design and Methodology

Pre-service teachers enrolled in the Professional Masters of Education (PME) programme in three different universities were invited to take part in this research study. Pre-service teachers were asked to complete a questionnaire at one of their general education lectures at the beginning of their second year on the PME. There were 204 pre-service teachers who completed this questionnaire.

Section C of the questionnaire consisted of 7 numeracy tasks in total; however, the numeracy tasks were presented in 6 questions. The first two numeracy tasks were part of question 1. Table 1 presents a short explanation of each numeracy task in the questionnaire. Pre-service teachers were asked to display their workings for each task in a text box provided.

Asking pre-service teachers to provide mathematical workings in the space provided enabled the authors to identify if the answer was correct or incorrect and furthermore allowed the authors to understand the pre-service teachers' mathematical thinking. Three of the numeracy tasks were published by the OECD as PISA test questions: Earthquake task (PISA, 2003), Car task (PISA, 2003) and the Salad dressing task (PISA, 2012). The other three numeracy tasks were developed specifically for this study.

Table 1

Explanation of each Numeracy task in the questionnaire

Numeracy tasks	Explanation
Time task	Calculate the difference between two Olympic swimmers' finishing race times for a 100 metre butterfly race. The results were presented in a table and the pre-service teachers had to subtract one decimal number from another decimal number ($51.14 - 50.39$)
Distance task	Joseph Schooling had a result of 50.39 in the 100 metre race and if the race was 30 metres longer, given that he was travelling at the same average speed as he did in the first race, calculate the new time he would finish the 130 metre race.
Earthquake task	A documentary about earthquakes and how often they occur is broadcast. A geologist stated "In the next twenty years, the chance that an earthquake will occur in Zed City is two out of three". Pre-service teachers were asked to use mathematical knowledge and understanding of statistics to predict an event occurring in this specific context. Pre-service teachers were provided with 4 different scenarios and asked to choose which one best reflected the meaning of the geologists statement.
Pie-chart task	Given a pie-chart, calculate the proportion of the pie chart (as a percentage) that represented the participants who chose biology as a subject for the Leaving Certificate.
Best Car task	Calculate the score of the "Best Car" given an equation. The "Best Car" is evaluated based on scores for safety features (S), fuel efficiency (F), external appearance (E) and internal fittings (T) and these were the variables in the given equation $(Ca) = (3 \times S) + F + E + T$. Pre-service teachers had to substitute values into the equation and work out the final answer for the Best Car.
Salad dressing task	A recipe for 100mls of salad dressing has three ingredients which are Salad Oil (60mls), Vinegar (30mls) and Soy sauce (10mls). Pre-service teachers were asked to calculate how much salad oil is required to make 175mls of salad dressing.
Mobile Phone task	David uses 500 minutes per month and 15GB of data. Recommend the best mobile phone plan for David, given price tariffs for 3 mobile phone companies.

In addition to completing the numeracy tasks, pre-service teachers were asked to indicate their level of confidence (Confident, Not Confident or Unsure) in each answer being correct. Pre-service teachers' responses could therefore be analysed to compare correctness and confidence for each numeracy task.

Findings

Pre-service teachers were asked to indicate whether they felt "confident", "not confident" or "unsure" that their answer was correct for each numeracy task they completed. Some participants chose to leave the confidence questions blank. Table 2 displays the confidence levels which pre-service teachers chose when answering each numeracy task.

Table 2

Frequency of self-reported confidence levels for each numeracy task

Numeracy tasks	Confident N(%)	Not Confident N(%)	Unsure N (%)	Blank N(%)
Time task	161 (78.9%)	23 (11.3%)	19 (9.3%)	1 (0.5%)
Distance task	75 (36.8%)	63 (30.9%)	38 (18.6%)	28 (13.7%)
Earthquakes task	141 (69.1%)	31 (15.2%)	27 (13.2%)	5 (2.5%)
Pie-chart task	115 (56.4%)	47 (23%)	22 (10.8%)	20 (9.8%)
Best Car task	134 (65.7%)	31 (15.2%)	20 (9.8%)	19 (9.3%)
Salad dressing task	101 (49.5%)	45 (22.1%)	30 (14.7%)	28 (13.7%)
Mobile Phone task	28 (13.7%)	56 (27.5%)	37 (18.1%)	83 (40.7%)

Overall the pre-service teachers displayed a high level of confidence in most of the answers they had provided. The distance task, which was part of question 1, saw a lower level in pre-service teachers' confidence with just over one third of participants stating they were confident in the answer they had provided. This may be because pre-service teachers had to calculate a new time for finishing the race if it was 30 metres longer. Some pre-service teachers may not have carried out this type of numeracy task since they were in school themselves. The final question, which was the mobile phone task, involved much more mathematical computation than any other numeracy task and this question was the least frequently answered question. In relation to confidence in the answers pre-service teachers provided for the mobile phone task, a total of 121 (59.3%) answered the confidence question. This was the only question for which there were more pre-service teachers not confident in the answer they had provided than any other question they had answered previously. One reason pre-service teachers may have had lower confidence in their answer could be that there was too much mathematical computation and thinking needed to answer this question and those who answered may have just written down an answer without providing any evidence of their mathematical procedures

to support their answer. The following section presents the analysis of comparisons between pre-service teachers' confidence and their ability to complete the tasks correctly.

Comparison between pre-service teachers' confidence and correctness

In order to compare pre-service teachers' confidence and their ability to answer the numeracy tasks correctly, four confidence categories were created:

- Category 1: Confidence Aligned (Confident and correct or not confident and incorrect)
- Category 2: Under Confident (Correct and not confident)
- Category 3: Over Confident (Incorrect and confident)
- Category 4: Unable to assess confidence (Sum of Unsure categories)

The results of this analysis are presented in Table 3.

Table 3

Comparison between confidence categories and numeracy tasks

	Confidence Aligned	Under Confident	Over Confident	Unable to assess confidence
Time Task	104 (51.7%)	9 (4.5%)	70 (34.8%)	18 (9%)
Distance Task	95 (58.7%)	19 (11.7%)	13 (8%)	35 (21.6%)
Earthquake Task	137 (68.8%)	20 (10.1%)	15 (7.5%)	27 (13.6%)
Pie-chart Task	130 (72.2%)	9 (5%)	21 (11.7%)	20 (11.1%)
Car Task	138 (76.2%)	19 (10.5%)	7 (3.9%)	17 (9.4%)
Salad Dressing Task	109 (63.7%)	17 (10%)	18 (10.5%)	27 (15.8%)
Mobile Phone Task	45 (38.8%)	17 (14.7%)	18 (15.5%)	36 (31%)

The Time task saw just over 50% of pre-service teachers align their confidence accurately, indicating that they were confident and correct, or not confident and incorrect. Furthermore, the Time task was the task where a considerable number of pre-service teachers (N=70, 34.8%) displayed over-confidence, in that they indicated they were confident their answer was correct, when in fact it was incorrect. It was interesting to observe the prevalence of over-confidence amongst pre-service teachers who obtained an incorrect answer. Confidence is often implicated in definitions of numeracy (e.g., DES, 2011; Goos et al., 2019), but this usually manifests as lack of confidence amongst those with poor numeracy capabilities. These findings present some worrying trends where some pre-service teachers exhibited confidence when the answer they provided was incorrect. This could have a negative effect on students' learning if these pre-service teachers continue to possess a sense of over confidence when it comes to teaching for numeracy learning within their classroom. The Mobile Phone task was

the only task whereby less than 40% (N=45) of the pre-service teachers who answered the confidence question managed to align their confidence and correctness of the task and this was also the task with the highest number of pre-service teachers who were unable to assess whether they were confident or not in their answer. The next section presents the analysis on pre-service teachers' confidence in relation to subject specialism.

Comparisons between pre-service teachers' confidence in correctness and subject specialism

It may be reasonable to assume that pre-service teachers in the STEM disciplines would be more confident in their ability to complete the numeracy tasks correctly than pre-service teachers in other disciplines. O'Sullivan and Goos (2022) revealed that pre-service teachers in the STEM disciplines believed they were better equipped and had enough mathematical knowledge to teach numeracy than pre-service teachers of non-STEM disciplines. Pearson Chi-square tests and Fisher exact tests were conducted to check if there was an association between pre-service teachers' confidence in completing the tasks correctly and Subject specialism of the pre-service teacher.

Analysis found that there was a statistically significant association between pre-service teachers' confidence in completing six of the numeracy questions correctly and their subject disciplines. Further analysis identified pre-service teachers in the STEM discipline possessing more confidence in completing the numeracy tasks correctly than any other discipline. However, it was interesting to see the results for the Mobile Phone task, as this was the only numeracy task that did not show a statistically significant difference between pre-service teachers' confidence and their subject discipline. This means the Mobile Phone task was the only numeracy task that pre-service teachers in the STEM discipline were not more confident in completing correctly. Table 4 presents the number of pre-service teachers in each discipline who were confident their answer to each numeracy task was correct. The most striking observation was that pre-service teachers from the STEM disciplines possessed a very high confidence in their answers with over 80% of them confident that their answer was correct for six of the numeracy tasks, however this fell to less than 40% for the mobile phone task.

Table 4

Cross tabulation of pre-service teachers' subject discipline against their confidence in completing each numeracy task correctly

Confidence in correctness	STEM (% within discipline)	Sociology (% within discipline)	Practical (% within discipline)	Languages (% within discipline)
Time Task	34 (97.1%)	37 (77.1%)	14 (58.3%)	76 (80%)
Distance Task	28 (84.8%)	16 (41%)	7 (35%)	24 (28.9%)
Earthquake Task	30 (88.2%)	35 (74.5%)	12 (50%)	64 (68.8%)
Pie Chart Task	30 (90.9%)	25 (55.6%)	9 (45%)	51(60%)
Best Car Task	33 (97.1%)	32 (76.2%)	12 (57.1%)	57 (65.5%)

Salad Dressing Task	30 (93.8%)	23 (54.8%)	11 (52.4%)	37 (46.3%)
Mobile Phone Task	10 (38.5%)	5 (19.2%)	2 (15.4%)	11 (19.6%)

Conclusion

Forgasz and Hall (2019) argue that pre-service teachers' confidence includes not only their own abilities and understandings, but also their willingness to teach for numeracy learning and their confidence in doing so. Researchers argue that demonstrating positive dispositions towards numeracy learning is essential in teaching for numeracy learning (Goos et al. 2019). If pre-service teachers are not confident in their own numeracy capabilities and not confident in their ability to teach for numeracy learning, then they must work towards building and developing their own mathematical knowledge and confidence in mathematical capabilities prior to teaching numeracy for disciplinary learning. Forgasz and Hall's (2019) research in the field of teacher education and numeracy learning, shows that students need to also be supported in this endeavour and this support can be offered in their ITE programmes.

Analysis from this research study demonstrated the differences between STEM and non-STEM pre-service teachers and found that teachers qualifying in a STEM discipline were significantly better at completing the numeracy tasks correctly and more confident in their answers to the numeracy tasks. This finding is an issue of concern, because if pre-service teachers of all disciplines are to teach numeracy for disciplinary learning within their lessons, regardless of their subject discipline, then pre-service teachers of all disciplines will need to have an adequate level of numeracy themselves in order to support numeracy development within their specific subject discipline. Callingham et al. (2015) advocate that all teachers, irrespective of their subject discipline, need to be given the opportunity to learn about the nature of numeracy within their subject. Furthermore, the Teaching Council of Ireland (2020) have agreed that teachers need to develop their personal numeracy knowledge and also specified that all universities involved in preparing pre-service teachers must provide appropriate support. Researchers argue that a person needs to be comfortable and confident to use mathematical knowledge to solve real world problems (Goos et al., 2019; Venkat & Winter, 2015). If pre-service teachers are lacking confidence in their own numeracy capabilities, this may in turn have an effect on how they embed numeracy learning in their lessons. Therefore, it is crucial that pre-service teachers are afforded the opportunities to develop positive dispositions towards numeracy learning.

References

- Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority [ACARA]. *General capabilities*. <https://www.australiancurriculum.edu.au/f-10-curriculum/general-capabilities/>
- Bolstad, O. H. (2019). Teaching for mathematical literacy: School leaders' and teachers' rationales. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/11250/2607685>
- Callingham, R., Beswick, K., & Ferme, E. (2015). An initial exploration of teachers' numeracy in the context of professional capital. *ZDM*, 47(4), 549-560.

- Department of Education and Skills [DES]. (2011). *Literacy and numeracy learning for life: The national strategy to improve literacy and numeracy among children and young people 2011–2020*. Dublin: DES. Retrieved from https://www.education.ie/en/Publications/Policy-Reports/lit_num_strategy_full.pdf
- Department of Education and Skills [DES] (2015). *Framework for Junior Cycle 2015*. Dublin: DES. Retrieved from <https://www.ncca.ie/media/3249/framework-for-junior-cycle-2015-en.pdf>
- Forgasz, H., & Leder, G. (2016). Numeracy and Australian Teachers. In White, B., Chinnappan, M. & Trenholm, S. (Eds.). *Opening up mathematics education research (Proceedings of the 39th annual conference of the Mathematics Education Research Group of Australasia)*, pp. 238–245. Adelaide: MERGA.
- Forgasz, H., & Hall, J. (2019). Learning about numeracy: The impact of a compulsory unit on pre-service teachers’ understandings and beliefs. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 44(2). <http://dx.doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2018v44n2.2>
- Goos, M., Geiger, V., Dole, S., Forgasz, H., & Bennison, A. (2019). *Numeracy across the curriculum: Research-based strategies for enhancing teaching and learning*. Sydney: Allen and Unwin.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (2003). PISA Test Questions. Retrieved from <https://www.oecd.org/education/school/programme-for-international-student-assessment-pisa/test-questions-pisa-2003.htm>
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (2013). PISA 2012 Released Mathematics Items. Retrieved from <https://www.oecd.org/pisa/pisaproducts/pisa2012-2006-rel-items-maths-ENG.pdf>
- O’ Sullivan, K., & Goos, M. (2022). Numeracy Across the Curriculum in Initial Teacher Education. In N. Fitzallen, C. Murphy, V. Hatisaru & N. Maher (Eds.), *Mathematical Confluences and Journeys (Proceedings of the 44th Annual Conference of the Mathematics Education Research Group of Australasia, July 3-7)* pp. 434–441. Launceston: MERGA.
- The Teaching Council of Ireland (2011) Initial teacher education: Criteria and guidelines for programme providers. Retrieved from <https://www.teachingcouncil.ie/en/publications/ite-professional-accreditation/criteria-and-guidelines-for-programme-providers-march-2017-.pdf>
- The Teaching Council of Ireland (2020) Céim: Standards for Initial Teacher Education. Retrieved from <https://www.teachingcouncil.ie/en/publications/ite-professional-accreditation/ceim-standards-for-initial-teacher-education.pdf>
- Venkat, H., Winter, M. Boundary objects and boundary crossing for numeracy teaching. *ZDM Mathematics Education* 47, 575–586 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-015-0683-6>